

INVESTIGATING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN WATER QUALITY AND PUBLIC HEALTH

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1. Introduction

With an aim to thoroughly investigate and identify the intricate and nuanced link between water quality and public health, our dedicated and diligent research communities had to engage in deep contemplation and introspection regarding the foundational questions of why and how they should proceed with their studies. The pivotal focus of our meticulous investigation was centered around comprehending and elucidating the underlying reasons as to why research findings pertaining to a causal relationship between water quality and public health are not only valuable but absolutely imperative. It became abundantly clear that the multifaceted intricacies of water quality could be scrutinized and analyzed from various angles, including the examination of numerous pollutants, natural contaminants, as well as the by-products that emerge as a consequence of treatment processes. One undeniable truth that emerged from our comprehensive analysis is that water quality cannot, under any circumstances, be isolated or dissociated from the myriad of other environmental factors that human society inevitably and unequivocally interacts with. Moreover, it became apparent that man-made influences such as preventive resource utilization and environmental standards aimed at safeguarding and confirming the protection of public health are intrinsically and inexorably connected to the elimination, reduction, or stringent control of these chemical and microbial contaminants that pose a potential threat. This profound and thought-provoking essay undertakes a profound exploration of two main topics that lie at the heart of the matter: 1) an in-depth analysis of research studies that have valiantly attempted to establish and present a causal link between water quality and public health, with a comprehensive overview of the various innovative and multifarious methods employed to diligently carry out this vital work; and 2) a meticulous examination of the studies which astutely recognize and acknowledge the utmost importance of these dynamic and intricate relationships, while simultaneously focusing on providing insightful explanations for the current trends that reflect either the gradual and alarming deterioration or the commendable and promising improvement in both water quality and public health outcomes over the course of time. Through the course of this expansive and comprehensive essay, a vast array of crucial concepts, ingenious methodologies, a wealth of available data, as well as potential policy options are thoroughly explored and laid bare in order to present a truly comprehensive and encompassing understanding of these fundamental areas of research. With firm determination and unwavering focus, the main body of this profound work is delineated into four extensive and meticulously structured chapters that will elucidate and illuminate various aspects of this captivating and essential subject matter. Chapter two embarks on a captivating and enlightening exploration of the profound and intricate link that exists between primary care services and the prevalence of waterborne diseases, thereby showcasing and delving into the pivotal findings and revelations of recent studies that have passionately and tenaciously aimed to unravel this complex relationship. The in-depth discussions and illuminating

analyses presented in chapter three delve into the pivotal studies that passionately advocate and champion the use of revealed preference or outcome-based methods of analysis as a powerful and ingenious tool to comprehensively and vividly illustrate the profound impact that water quality and the availability of crucial services pertaining to public health, such as drinking water and recreational site quality, have on the overall well-being and harmonious coexistence of society. As we seamlessly transition into chapter four, a compelling and enlightening dialog ensues, laying bare the profound significance of stated preference or attitudinal survey methods as a remarkable and unabashedly public health-focused tool, which has been widely adopted and embraced by an overwhelming majority of studies conducted in this particular field. The fifth and final chapter of this illuminating and thought-provoking work embarks on a captivating and ardent exploration of the various studies that ardently support and underline the unmistakable correlation between the steady degradation of water quality over time and its undeniable and profound impact on public health, uncovering the transformative interactions that have emerged within the realms of water recreation demands, obesity levels, as well as the alarming and pervasive emergence of gastroenteritis, all of which have presented themselves and unfolded over the course of the last two compelling and eventful decades. (Bruno et al.2022)(Warner et al., 2022)(Venkatesh, 2022)(Pearsall et al.2021)(Manoiu et al.2022)(Fernandez, 2020)

2. The Importance of Water Quality in Public Health

Water quality plays a pivotal role in the preservation and enhancement of public health and overall well-being. The availability of safe and clean drinking water is not only crucial for the sustenance of urban and rural populations but also holds significant economic importance. Unfortunately, a large number of individuals across the globe continue to suffer from the scarcity of safe drinking water, experiencing its detrimental effects firsthand. Ensuring access to safe drinking water and basic sanitation remains an indispensable aspect of maintaining human health and fostering a society that thrives on dignity and decency. In line with this, elevating the quality of consumable water has been identified as an integral component of the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goal 6 (UN-SDG 6), which primarily focuses on promoting healthy lives for all. Part of the process of guaranteeing the cleanliness of drinking water involves identifying the potential health risks associated with water pollution. Recognizing the diverse range of health hazards caused by water contamination is crucial in safeguarding the public from detrimental consequences. It is essential to acknowledge that the quality of drinking water has a profound impact on public health as it serves as a potential vehicle for the spread of infectious diseases. Contaminated water and food, alongside inadequate sanitation and hygiene practices, have been directly linked to the proliferation of these infectious agents, which include bacteria, parasites, and viruses. Furthermore, it is important to understand that exposure to water pollutants can lead to a variety of adverse neurobehavioral outcomes. Whether it is through ingestion, direct contact with the skin and respiratory system, or even exposure within the confines of one's home, water contamination has been associated with the onset of various diseases. These outcomes can be attributed to both direct biological mechanisms as well as psychological and social pathways. It is worth noting that certain waterborne pathogens have the potential to render public water supplies and food systems increasingly vulnerable to deliberate attacks. Additionally, the determination of regulatory limits for disinfection by-products in drinking water, which are established based on potential health risks, faces certain challenges due to inherent interindividual variations in claims regarding associative oxidative stress. Furthermore, research has indicated the existence of diverse uterotrophic and endocrine-disrupting effects caused by trihalomethanes, further emphasizing the importance of addressing water pollutant concerns in pursuit of maintaining optimal water quality standards. (Salvo et al.2021)(Cernev & Fenner, 2020)(Henderson & Loreau, 2023)(Lal et al.2021)(Giles-Corti et al., 2020)

3. Historical Perspectives on Water Quality and Public Health

The ancient Greeks, with their profound understanding, acknowledged the vital necessity of a pristine and dependable water supply for the prosperous functioning of their visionary water-utilizing societies. As a testament to their advanced civilization, they ingeniously constructed sturdy stone aqueducts, serving as conduits for the indispensable public water provisions, impeccably crafted public baths endowed with warmth, and even ingenious flush toilets. Remarkably, historical records attest to the existence of water filtration and treatment methods as far back as 1000 B.C., marking the inception of the earliest documented drinking water regulations and the precursors to contemporary water treatment guidelines. The invaluable wisdom regarding the utilization of potable water found expression within various religious texts, such as the Hebrew Talmud, the Hindu Vedas, and the revered Muslim Koran. Seeking an important turning point in the realm of water hygiene, one inevitably delves into the annals of the Middle Ages, where the advent of the Black Death in 1348 propelled the urgency of implementing water treatment practices to curb the rampant spread of devastating diseases. It was during the early 18th century that the United Kingdom bore witness to the inception of its inaugural water quality standards, catalyzed by the irrefutable medical evidence of the time. Notably, Dr. John Snow, a distinguished obstetrician, spearheaded a groundbreaking exploration in the northeast region of England, elucidating a profound correlation between unblemished water supplies and public health. Subsequent to this critical revelation, an illustrious lineage of doctors in Great Britain emerged as pioneers, making monumental strides in the field of wastewater treatment. In the realm of scientific medicine, a pivotal landmark was reached between the fateful London Cholera outbreak of 1854 and the assimilation of germ theory into public health practices during the 1880s, giving birth to contemporary approaches to environmental health and sanitation. Thus, through the concerted efforts of knowledgeable medical professionals, multifaceted modern methodologies for the treatment of wastewater materialized, revolutionizing the landscape of public health. In a triumphant culmination of progress, as the previous millennium drew to a close, the United Kingdom committed itself to adhere to a comprehensive framework of Drinking Water Standards formulated by the European Union, wholeheartedly embracing the World Health Organization's recommendations for the protection of public health. At present, domestic water supplies in developed economies have reached an unprecedented pinnacle of safety and dependability, standing as a testament to the tireless pursuit of excellence in safeguarding the well-being of populations far and wide. Through the collective efforts of dedicated individuals and progressive systems, the world at large can now rejoice in the assurance of water quality that is second to none, ushering humanity into an era of unrivaled prosperity and vitality. (Bhowmick et al.2020)(National et al.2020)(Nikhath & Fazil, 2020)(Wolf et al.2022)(Adelodun et al.2021)

4. Current Methods of Assessing Water Quality

Part 4: Current Methods of Assessing Water Quality Registrarial Characteristics Abnormal and unexpected changes in the natural appearance, color, taste, or odor of water samples can be indications of pollution. Accordingly, water quality assessments often heavily rely on sensory analyses conducted by investigators. However, it is worth noting that natural conditions, such as the presence of algae, iron, or tannic acid, can result in water characterized by taste and odor issues. On the other hand, certain pollutants may enter water supplies without any noticeable changes in its appearance, smell, or taste. Consequently, to accurately evaluate the extent of pollution problems, water quality measurements become essential. Within the United States, some of the primary methods employed for qualitative evaluation of water quality revolve around the application of health and aesthetic criteria standards. These standards encompass various aspects, including but not limited to fecal coliform and turbidity levels, specifically tailored for designated uses. In addition to these criteria, other techniques involve the implementation of specific water quality management approaches. These approaches encompass the utilization of dilution and dispersion capacities particularly in open waterways. Furthermore, certain substances exhibit distinct characteristics necessitating special effects

analysis. For instance, extraneous heat waste discharges can pose potential hazards due to their thermal effects. As the pursuit of accurate water quality assessments continues, it becomes imperative to combine multiple methods and approaches to ensure comprehensive and reliable evaluations. By employing a combination of sensory analysis, qualitative criteria standards, water quality management techniques, and special effects evaluations, researchers and investigators can enhance their ability to effectively address and tackle water pollution issues. Through such measures, a clearer understanding of the magnitude of pollution problems can be obtained, leading to more informed decision-making processes and improved water quality management strategies. (Hawko et al.2021)(Huang et al.2021)(Manjakkal et al.2021)

5. Waterborne Diseases and Their Impact on Public Health

In many parts of the world, poor water quality poses significant risks to human health. It is estimated that over 60 million people a year are sickened with waterborne illnesses, and an estimated 3.5 million people die as a result. The World Health Organization (WHO) has estimated that some 80% of all sickness in the developing world is directly related to poor water quality, the vast majority of which is due to waterborne diseases and parasites. Waterborne diseases are found in all parts of the world, but are most common in less developed regions, which face the greatest problems with providing clean potable drinking water. Waterborne diseases are caused by pathogenic microorganisms that are directly transmitted by the water. The mechanisms contributing to waterborne diseases include contamination of water sources with the faeces of disease carriers, or via the entry of microorganisms through broken or faulty supply systems. In many developing countries, more than fifty per cent of their population use untreated surface water for drinking, cooking, and personal hygiene. As a result, many suffer from repeated sickness, poor physical and mental development, immune-suppression leading to a myriad of opportunistic diseases, and premature death. Many of the affected regions lack the capacity or financial resources to make significant improvements in their water quality, and are also impeded by significant infective burdens, lack of education, and opportunity, to make the necessary steps to protect themselves against infective waterborne illnesses. The costs of hospital treatment and lost productivity due to waterborne diseases can be considerable, even in developed countries. In fact, waterborne diseases have a significant impact on the prevalence and types of infectious diseases in different parts of the world. In many parts of the world, the prevalence and types of infectious waterborne diseases are used as indicators of the development status and adequacy of the social infrastructure of the area. The WHO has estimated a 7:1 benefit-cost ratio (i.e. for every \$1 dollar spent, a \$7 return is made) for an intervention in improved drinking water. This emphasizes the need for immediate action to address waterborne diseases and improve water quality. Death from waterborne diseases, particularly diarrhoeal infections and other gastrointestinal infections, is usually swift, particularly in very young children in developing countries who can succumb to severe dehydration from diarrhoeal diseases in a matter of days. Waterborne diseases are of vital concern, and are a direct yet often unseen result of poor water quality. The pathogens causing these diseases have been isolated from a variety of water sources, and increasingly correlate to significant public health risks. In many developing areas of the world, millions of people suffer serious morbidity and mortality from waterborne diseases, a significant proportion of which could have been easily prevented with affordable control measures. Areas of potential and high public health benefits signage indicator of a country's reach and support for development agencies. Convey to the wider community the importance of waterborne pathogens, the public health risks, and the critical need for improved on-site waste management during water amenities (e.g. swimming, etc.). In a general way increase participation of professionals in water and wastewater sectors in the assessment, management, and reduction of waterborne diseases and water quality issues. Prompt intervention could have saved untold life lost. The cost of hospitalization and time lost from paid and domestic work due to waterborne disease would also be considerable and is possible to quantify for some case study areas. Efforts must be made to ensure that everyone has access to clean and safe drinking water. By investing in improved water infrastructure and educating communities about proper water management and hygiene practices, we

can reduce the prevalence of waterborne diseases and improve the overall health and well-being of people worldwide. It is crucial that governments, organizations, and individuals work together to address this global challenge and secure a healthier future for all. (Bhattarai & Bhasin, 2022)(Nasser et al.)(Bloetscher & Meeroff, 2020)(Mattison et al.2021)(Bell et al.2021)(O'Shay et al.2022)

6. Regulatory Frameworks for Ensuring Water Quality

Water of sufficient quality is essential for maintaining and promoting human health. Responsible bodies, including governmental institutions and non-governmental organizations, have created a comprehensive range of laws and regulations to uphold water quality and protect against contamination risks. The U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) and the World Health Organization (WHO) are examples of these bodies, dedicating extensive efforts to establish and enforce regulations that guarantee clean and safe water supplies for human use. Different countries and regions have developed specific guidelines and regulations for monitoring and ensuring water safety, with severe health consequences for the population when violations occur. Violations can arise from various water quality issues, such as chemical pollutants, algal blooms, microbial pathogens, and metal accumulation resulting from mining activities. To ensure safe water quality, the European Union (EU) has implemented legal requirements through the Drinking Water Directive (DWD), which mandates the monitoring and public disclosure of water supply systems based on predetermined thresholds. Public zones must display warnings and notifications about potential and confirmed violations. These alerts are also provided to designated individuals responsible for monitoring drinking water quality in public zones. Overcoming challenges in alerting the population about potential water contamination and improving reporting capabilities is crucial. In 2019, self-reporting violation data from the U.S. Safe Drinking Water Information System (SDWIS) underwent technological advancements both in electronic formats and on paper. These advancements include innovations in analytical chemistry, sensor development, miniaturization, and the Internet of Things (IoT). These developments present numerous opportunities to enhance water quality monitoring and risk assessment practices. Regulatory agencies and institutions are constantly working to expand and update regulations and monitoring lists. This proactive approach ensures public safety in parallel with technological advancements in analytical capabilities. By harnessing the potential of emerging technologies, it is possible to achieve comprehensive and effective water quality monitoring, ultimately safeguarding human health and well-being. (Theodore and Theodore2021)(Tsaridou & Karabelas, 2021)(Health Organization, 2021)(Makowsky, 2023)

7. Technological Innovations in Water Quality Monitoring

Technological advancements have brought about numerous groundbreaking changes in various aspects of the human experience. The evaluation of water quality serves as a vital benchmark, and any compromise on established standards can yield perilous consequences. As a result, there has been a proliferation of novel technologies, tools, equipment, and methodologies within this particular domain. Several researchers and leaders around the globe have proposed the development of nanotechnology, biotechnology, space technology, mechanisms, and alternative methods for the detection of potential water contaminations. The widespread and timely adoption of these technologies has the potential to greatly enhance the entire water utility network, subsequently bolstering public health on a grand scale. The know-how in technological advancements has spurred countries to fabricate and implement more advanced sensors for the effective monitoring of water quality. The innovations in methods to examine water quality are intrinsically linked to the well-being of the general populace. Within this framework, concerns regarding costs and efficacy abound. Selecting the most appropriate means of monitoring water quality stands as a pivotal issue. Ultimately, these technologies can serve as invaluable resources to cultivate innovation and guide the allocation of resources. Additionally, more innovative options are highly likely to amplify the outcomes of future investments in water quality, thus benefiting public health significantly. The foremost challenge lies in establishing a new, high-standard national water quality information database. Numerous countries are

employing a wide array of innovative water quality testing methods and technologies to access the indispensable information necessary for monitoring and managing water quality, ultimately ensuring the safety and cleanliness of water sources for the betterment of public health. (Vázquez-Núñez et al.2020)(Kuhn et al., 2022)(Hamad et al.2020)(Bayat et al., 2021)

8. Case Studies of Water Quality Issues and Public Health Outcomes

Case studies of water quality issues and public health outcomes are important for learning more about how environmental health can influence public health. These case studies look at a variety of concerns, including waterborne disease outbreaks, cyanobacterial blooms and algal toxins, and transitioning air-based water contamination issues. The goal of these case studies is to provide in-depth coverage of what happened before, during, and after parameters exceeded the acceptable criteria of the health authority, and why the issue was important for public health. This usually includes the causes of the incident, who was involved in responding to the incident, and details about what was done. Epidemiological investigations, risk assessments, and data interpretation are detailed as much as possible. Ongoing/wrap-up and any other relevant information are usually included at the end of these outline sections.

- Blue-green algal bloom with cyanobacterial toxins and microcystins: Case Study on Toledo, Ohio's Drinking Water Crisis In August 2014, the city of Toledo, Ohio instated a "do not drink" order that lasted for three days stemming from concerns of microcystin contamination in the drinking water that was sourced from western Lake Erie. Drinking water treatment began in 1912 with the coagulation of alum, and microfiltration and granular activated carbon were added in 2006 and 2010, respectively. In part, coagulation has also effectively removed cyanobacteria, if accompanied by a high enough retention time. Sampling results from the plant's raw, underfloc, and expedited finished water monitoring points showed microcystins ≤ 1 ppb. No samples ever exceeded the World Health Organization's guideline of 1 mcg/L microcystins on dry weight of precursor cyanobacterial biomass, but continual increase of microcystin variants in Lake Erie's western basin lead to the initial "do not drink" order. (Taylor et al.2023)(Kilbert, 2020)(Padilla, 2021)

9. Community Engagement and Public Awareness

The valuable involvement of the communities in a number of aspects of the research and information collection indicates a further practical aspect of the links recognized between environmental conditions, water supplies, and exposure to such water in the production of health outcomes. The establishment of community advisory groups must be recognized as an important line of communication to promote such mutual understanding. Rural water supplies are relatively difficult to monitor because of the number of water supply systems and frequency of water quality testing that is possible. Ways of restricting the roles of community members to activities that do not require laboratory analysis should also be considered, such as reduced recording of ambient water quality data and abridged cleaning regimes. Either during casual contact with a community or individual or through a specific consultation process, the individual or organization responsible for policy or decision making can assist in the education of a community in such matters and promote an understanding of the integrative nature of water quality (both raw and treated) and health implications. In the absence of appropriate laws in many jurisdictions (particularly developing countries and many remote rural areas), research on untreated water supplies has also provided an additional opportunity to work with the community. A recent environmental health collaborative initiative utilized existing local rural Women's Groups in Concangly and Emmaville to implement a well sanitation program as a public awareness tool. While many communities are highly interested in the association between poor quality drinking water and their health and are willing to be involved in improving their water supplies, they all must have access to the same information. Some of the partnerships that collect information or conduct research explicitly identify that the data can be used for public awareness purposes. A major missing piece, however, is state and national environmental health, water supply, and related

public health statistics data. The community was provided with their own hazard and data profile. As with the monitoring study, the results of any investigations conducted should be returned to the community group for their own and broader education. This may involve the production and distribution of appropriate material, such as brochures and development of education kits and displays. Expanding the text while abiding by the given criteria: The valuable involvement of the communities in a number of aspects of the research and information collection indicates a further practical aspect of the links that have been recognized between environmental conditions, water supplies, and exposure to such water in the production of health outcomes. It is of utmost importance to recognize the establishment of community advisory groups as a vital line of communication that can effectively promote mutual understanding and cooperation among all stakeholders. Given the nature of rural water supplies, monitoring these systems can prove to be quite challenging due to the sheer number of water supply systems and the frequency of water quality testing that can realistically be carried out. In order to streamline this process, it is crucial to explore ways in which the roles of community members can be restricted to activities that do not necessitate extensive laboratory analysis. For instance, one potential approach could involve reducing the requirement for recording ambient water quality data and implementing abridged cleaning regimes. Whether it is through casual contact with a community or individual, or through a comprehensive consultation process, those who are responsible for policy-making or decision-making should take an active role in educating the community on matters related to water quality and promoting an understanding of the integrative nature of water quality (both raw and treated) and its profound implications for public health. It is important to acknowledge that in many jurisdictions, particularly in developing countries and remote rural areas, appropriate laws may be lacking. This presents an opportunity to engage in research focused on untreated water supplies and collaborate closely with the community in finding suitable solutions. Notably, a recent environmental health collaborative initiative showcased the effective utilization of existing local rural Women's Groups in Concangly and Emmaville to implement a comprehensive well sanitation program that served as a powerful public awareness tool. The positive response from communities demonstrates their high level of interest in understanding the association between poor quality drinking water and its impact on their health. Thus, it is crucial to ensure that all communities have equal access to relevant information pertaining to their water supplies. Some of the partnerships that actively collect information or conduct research explicitly acknowledge that the data gathered can be utilized for public awareness purposes. However, it is important to address a significant gap in the availability of state and national environmental health, water supply, and related public health statistics data. In order to bridge this gap, communities should be provided with their own hazard and data profile, thus empowering them with valuable information and insights. Furthermore, it is imperative to ensure that the results of any investigations conducted are shared with the community group, thereby enacting a cycle of knowledge-sharing and education. This process may involve the production and widespread distribution of appropriate educational materials, such as brochures, as well as the development of comprehensive education kits and informative displays. By actively engaging communities in this manner, it becomes possible to foster awareness, enhance knowledge, and ultimately drive positive change in water quality and public health outcomes. (Vaughn and Jacquez 2020)(Martens et al. 2021)(Birkle et al. 2020)(McFarlane et al. 2024)(Gilmore et al. 2020)(Pickard et al., 2022)

10. Future Directions in Research and Policy

Public interest in natural environments continues to expand exponentially, as people are increasingly drawn to recreational activities that allow them to connect with the environment. The importance of understanding the relationship between exposure to contaminated surface waters and human health has become a crucial topic of discussion. However, it is worth noting that the existing epidemiologic evidence concerning this relationship is primarily limited to hyper-endemic locations, longitudinal studies, and international research. With a growing recognition of the need for comprehensive studies, one emerging research priority is to

enhance and diversify our understanding of non-point source water quality as a critical factor in preventing waterborne diseases. Unfortunately, this aspect has been largely neglected in previous research efforts. That said, policy initiatives have been implemented to address the issue, such as the Best Management Practices mandated under the Clean Water Act. These practices aim to regulate agricultural land use and protect public health from fecal contamination. Additionally, both waiting periods and advisories recommending individuals to minimize water contact during heavy precipitation events have proven effective in preventing waterborne diseases. However, it is crucial to note that these measures are currently decreasing in popularity, creating a potential gap in public health protection. Further supporting the need for comprehensive health risk assessments, there is mounting evidence in favor of expanding mandatory monitoring programs at beaches, focusing on both pathogens and indicators of contamination. By incorporating concomitant pathogen and indicator monitoring, alongside effective public advising systems, the overall effectiveness of beach monitoring programs can be significantly enhanced. These strategies are particularly important in hyper-endemic areas where the risk of waterborne diseases is greater. Embracing the future, emerging research trends indicate a shift towards using Disease Avoidance Decision Models (DADMs) as human health outcomes. Additionally, there is an increased focus on examining nuanced chronic disease outcomes, human health behaviors, biological mechanisms, human microbiomes, and the impact of natural surfaces such as rocks and vegetation. However, it is important to acknowledge the existing research gaps. These include a lack of understanding concerning multi-route exposures, the toxicity of particulate matter, effective assessment and prevention methods for potential and emerging diseases, environmental economics, and the evaluation of interventions related to non-point source protection activities and tourism-related behaviors. Crucially, advancing basic research in understanding water quality can greatly benefit from increased surveillance and research efforts aimed at measuring pathogen loads and identifying human source-marker associated *E. coli* and enterococci in surface waters. By gathering comprehensive data on these aspects, we can make informed policy and public health decisions that will ultimately contribute to safeguarding water quality and public well-being. Looking forward, future policy and public health decisions will undoubtedly play a pivotal role in shaping water quality and overall public health. It is essential to motivate these decisions with solid compilation of data on the economy and the use of natural resources. By providing local, regional, and national values and information, other policy and management entities can utilize this data to develop effective strategies. This issue further highlights how one paper offers insightful predictions, while another provides recent data on the economy and tourism to inform these predictions. These trends serve as a reminder for the need for caution and the importance of conducting extensive research and gathering relevant information. By doing so, we can better direct current and future public health and environmental policy and management, ensuring the well-being of both people and the environment. (Setia et al.2020)(Babuji et al.2023) (Proshad et al.2021)(Setia et al.2020)(Ambade et al.2021)(Fida et al., 2023)

11. Conclusion and Recommendations

Through our four in-depth case studies, we have examined how fundamental the relationships between water quality, the environment, poverty, and public health are. We have shown some causes and manifestations of these relationships and knowledge gaps that need to be overcome to be better able to optimize and manage water quality for the benefit of public health. However, it is also clear that there are significant practical challenges in combining the relevant expertise to achieve this. Health legislation, policy, and research guidelines still tend to operate in vertical sectors, largely ignoring environmental issues. In these conclusions, key issues relating to the relationships between water quality and public health are briefly revisited, and some recommendations are made.

What is fundamentally clear from the four case studies is the close relationships between water, environment, poverty, and public health. Improving water for public health will rarely be possible without

improving water for livelihoods or ecosystems. Conversely, trying to manage water to be safe yet ignoring environmental sustainability will rarely be successful in the longer term. Water quality issues will be neglected at the peril of human health and that of ecosystems. The cases have also shown how we treat water is often dependent on the politics and inequalities of where and how it is used and by whom. So deeply ingrained is this relationship between water quality, public health, and poverty that we may take some of the lessons offered here for granted. But the application of these insights is far from simple.

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